

EDUCATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT SCHOOL

Elboeva Umida Rakhimdzhon kizi

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute Student of the faculty "Physical culture"

Annotation: This issue should be in the focus of the entire teaching staff when solving large-scale physical education tasks at school. Gone are the days when all the physical education issues at school were left to the physical education teacher alone.

Keywords: school, teacher, physical education, student, planning.

Experience in physical education has shown that educators who pay close attention to the planning of their work achieve high results. Plans allow you to look ahead, look ahead, set goals and clear objectives, ways to solve the tasks and sources of greater efficiency.

There are also cases of neglect of planning in practical work, which is a formality in planning, which is the first source of successful work. However, planning is not just a matter of putting it down on paper, it is a matter of copying the curriculum without thinking, but it is a process of getting a deeper insight into the nature and laws of physical education.

Planning is the ability to draw the right conclusions based on an analysis of work. Regular analysis of lessons shows the teacher the number of repetitions of the necessary physical exercises, the sequence of exercises, the volume of learning tasks and the norm of pedagogical activity, without which it is impossible to improve planning. Thus, planning is the creation of methodologically based documents that shape the learning and larvalization system.

This issue should be in the focus of the whole pedagogical team in solving large-scale physical education tasks in the school. Entrust all physical education issues in the school only to the physical education teacher period is over.

The various measures of this work should be addressed regularly in pedagogical councils and trade union meetings. All educators should take an active part in the development of physical education in all classes, in improving the ability of students to work, to develop their organizational skills, to have a positive impact on their will and achievement. In order to consolidate and direct the work of all members of the teaching staff at the school, to further improve the physical education of students, the Ministry of Public Education and the State Sports Committee approved the "Regulations on physical education of secondary school students." "Approved. The charter provides a

brief description of school responsibilities, forms of physical activity, and other aspects of student physical education.

According to the charter, all members of the teaching staff are responsible for the physical education of students in the school, in addition to their profession.

Every team should take a positive approach to physical education and sports to improve students' ability to work, improve discipline, and reduce child morbidity. From a lesson on physical education for teachers To summarize the description of extracurricular activities, it is important to note the following:

- the use of all forms of physical education at work, the effective use of each specific situation in solving the tasks;
- Ensuring 100% student participation in extracurricular activities, involving the entire pedagogical community, parents, parenting organizations and, if necessary, foundations;
- the form and content of the activities will be determined;
- Gradually create a base for the organization of extracurricular activities, to intensify advocacy work in the classroom and at school;
- Relying on public organizations is the work of experienced teachers;
- duplication and uniformity have never been successful;
- Every extracurricular activity should be carefully considered and evaluated.

This is achieved through the acquisition of theoretical information in the school curriculum, the development of physical qualities and the study of physical activity, as well as the setting of a number of specific tasks. Therefore, the next planning technology can be considered as the correct setting of educational tasks.

In order to solve the set tasks, the teacher determines the system of pedagogical influence on students. It includes resources, methods, and working conditions. the operation can be performed with the active participation of students, as before. It is important to take into account the negative factors that may hinder the proper organization of the physical education process.

A step-by-step control plan is developed using a specially selected test to verify that the pedagogical process is going well. If the control results obtained at one stage of the liar correspond to the planned ones, then it can be concluded that all the operational plans are correct. If the plans are made in good faith, but the results of the inspection are slightly different than planned, it means that there are errors in the planning technology.

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